

Alleviating The Risk of Sewer Flooding using Fuzzy Logic in a Real Time Control System – An Experimental Study

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Abstract

This paper proposes a data driven (Fuzzy Logic) control algorithm for use in a real time control (RTC) system within a combined sewer system. Implementation of local RTC will enable utilisation of the existing capacity within a sewer network and so alleviate the risk of sewer flooding using commercially available flow control solutions and a data driven approach. A full scale laboratory experiment will be utilised to test the proposed control algorithm using a vertical sluice gate.

Keywords

Fuzzy Logic; flooding; flow regulation; real time control

INTRODUCTION

The risk of urban flooding has been predicted to rise throughout the European Union (EU) (EEA, 2012). This was indicated by the European Environment Agency who also found that the risk of flooding is higher in the western and northern European states (EEA, 2012). Evans et al. (2004) and the Pitt Review (2008) estimate the costs of urban flooding to be in the region of £1-10billion by 2080 in the UK. The inability of sewer systems to store or convey a sufficient volume of rainfall run-off is a major factor that can increase the risk of flooding in urban areas. However, the increasing impermeable surface areas and the changes in storm profiles in recent years, due to climate change have increased the high risk of urban flooding in the EU. For example, more peaked storms overload the local sewer network more frequently and rapidly and so can consequently increase urban flood risk. Flooding causes economic damage, creates health risks and is a threat to the local natural environments. A typical response to urban flooding caused by inadequate hydraulic capacity is the upgrade of the sewer system through pipe replacement / refurbishment, expanding local storage capacity with new infrastructure or by installing Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) within urban areas to reduce run-off volumes into the existing sewer network. These options involve significant costs and are usually challenging for water utilities and local governments. For example, the city of Rotterdam is investing over €100,000,000 on urban flood prevention measures which include 240,000 m³ of extra urban storm water storage capacity as well as an extensive subsidy for green roof installation across the city (Vonk, 2006). This suggests that smaller local flood issues may not be dealt with in a timely or effective manner because of the lack of sufficient high funds to address all flood risk locations. The vast majority of sewers and piped drainage networks in the EU are currently passive systems, which means that operators are likely to have little control of the system during rainfall or flooding events. The size, complexity and varied elevations of sewer pipes in a network indicates that urban flooding may occur whilst there is large

under-utilised storage capacity available within the part of the urban drainage network upstream of a flood location. Therefore, there is a current need for a better exploitation of the combined sewers' storage using effective low costs techniques to reduce the risk of local flooding. Effective utilisation of existing assets can be implemented by deploying a Real Time Control (RTC) system to better manage local flows in the sewer network through the physical control of in-pipe flows. RTC systems can be effective, less costly than enlarging the physical capacity of the sewerage system, and can clearly improve the flood risk performance of existing drainage systems (Borsanyi et al., 2008; Ruggaber and Montestruque, 2007, Garcia-Gutierrez et al. 2015). Therefore, this paper proposes a new local autonomous and self-learning RTC system using flow attenuation devices in a combined sewer. The ultimate aim of the system is to reduce the local flood risk in urban areas. The system will therefore rely on knowledge of the hydraulics and incorporate efficient control algorithms. A great advantage of the system is being low cost with minimal infrastructure build and hence, it can be installed locally in high risk flooding urban areas. Figure 1 shows an example of how the proposed RTC can be integrated with a flow control mechanism to utilise sewer storage.

Figure 1: Implementation example of the proposed RTC system integrated with a flow control mechanism to utilise sewer storage.

METHODOLOGY

Fuzzy Logic (FL) was introduced by Zadeh (1968), and has been previously implemented in the UK water industry by researchers such as Ostojin et al. (2011) for sewer pumping station control. Fuzzy Logic is an approach derived from Fuzzy set theory in which parameters have degrees of membership ranging between 0 and 1 rather than strict binary values. It combines the simple rules of an expert system (coded as a Rule base) with a flexible specification of input and output parameters (expressed as Membership functions defined by the range and shape for each variable). An algorithmic strategy for ‘defuzzification’ is applied to obtain a single-valued output. The primary goal of the envisaged data driven algorithm is to control the flow attenuation devices’ control settings in order to utilise the capacity in the upstream sewer system and hence control the water level at a potential downstream flooding location. Thus, the risk of localised flooding can be reduced. The Fuzzy Logic input parameters are the water level in different sewer locations, while the output parameter is the opening level of the flow restriction mechanism. The flow attenuation mechanism proposed in this work is a vertical sluice gate, varying the gate opening regulates flows and therefore water levels upstream and downstream of the gate. Developing a robust FL system necessitates the understanding of the control mechanism’s (sluice gate) impact on the water levels

in the network. Hence, a full-scale laboratory facility will be conducted, where a vertical sluice gate is implemented in a 30 m long, 200 mm diameter pipe. In an attempt to replicate a real sewer pipe, the laboratory pipe will be fitted with four manholes with 1 m diameter and 1.5 m depth each, where water is running at a maximum flow rate of 50 L/s. The first manhole is designed to minimise vortices, while the second manhole contains an adjustable weir to control water level upstream of the system. The third manhole incorporates the vertical 200 mm diameter sluice gate, which is followed by a fourth manhole where water level downstream is measured. All manholes are to be connected inline by a 200 mm diameter pipe with a 1 in 500 slope. Manholes 1 and 2 are separated by 5 m while the rest of manholes are separated by 10 m. A control valve will be installed at the downstream end of the rig to control flows and water levels. The laboratory setup is illustrated in Figure 2 where every square is a representative of a manhole.

Figure 2: Laboratory setup. MH stands for manhole, DS and US denote downstream and upstream respectively.

The laboratory experiment will run a number of tests to better understand the relationship between gate opening and the consequent variation of water levels along the pipe profile. **Figure 3** shows the concept of the laboratory tests.

Figure 3: Concept of the proposed laboratory tests.

Flows are pumped into Manhole 1 and water levels upstream (US) and downstream (DS) of the sluice gate are measured and used as input parameters for the sluice gate control algorithm as illustrated by Figure 3. The relationship between gate opening and the variation of water levels (US and DS) can therefore be developed and ultimately utilised to optimise the FL algorithm.

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